

GA no 101081555

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

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Impetus4Change Project Manual

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Author	Megan Brunswig, Stefan Sobolowski
Summary	This Project Manual addresses the management Structures and Procedures (required for D8.1), and complements the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) by highlighting the most relevant items from the agreements in terms of obligations, deadlines, procedures, etc. It is a living document, and will be updated as necessary.

**Zenodo repository for I4C
open access documents**[Impetus4Change Community](https://zenodo.org/communities/impetus4change)

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Table 1: Abbreviations used in this document

AMGA	Annotated Model Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
CDE	Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan
CFS	Certificate of Financial Statement
DoA	Description of Action
DM	Data Manager
DMP	Data Management Plan
DTT	Demonstration Task Team
EAB	External Advisory Board
EC	European Commission
ECS	Early Career Scientist
EU	European Union
FM	Financial Manager
GA	Grant Agreement, or General Assembly
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
M	Month
MC	Management Committee
PC	Project Coordinator
PFSIGN	Project Financial Signatory
PM	Project Manager
PO	Project Coordinator Office
REA	Research Executive Agency
SSC	Scientific Steering Committee
TL	Task Leader
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

1 Summary

This Project Manual serves several purposes:

- It provides an overview of the project management structure, participation and processes;
- It complements the Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA) by highlighting the most relevant items from the agreements in terms of obligations, deadlines, procedures, etc.
- It provides useful guidance on reporting, links to templates, where to find important reference documents within the I4C folder structure, etc.

It is a living document, and will be updated as necessary (e.g. updates in contacts, folder links, procedures, etc.) or as further needs for clarifications and guidance appear throughout the project.

2 Definitions

In the Project Management Plan the following definitions apply:

- Participants - Entities participating in the action as beneficiaries, affiliated entities or associated partners
- Beneficiaries (BEN) — The signatories of the Consortium Agreement (either directly or through an accession form).
- Associated partners (AP) — Entities which participate in the action, but without the right to charge costs or claim contributions.
- Informal Partners (IP) – Entities which participate in the action, but have not signed the Consortium Agreement, nor the Grant Agreement, have no obligations or associated budget.

3 Introduction

The Project Manual intends to aid project partners on their tasks and how to fulfil them. It is a dynamic reference document for each partner in the I4C project and it will be updated as necessary. It provides details about the organisation of the project, specifically:

- Contact details of people working on the project, and procedures for updating this information
- Project organisation
- Management structure and procedures
- Deliverable preparation and delivery procedures
- Routines to meet reporting requirements from the European Commission (EC)
- Optimisation of communication flow within the consortium to facilitate implementation

The updated Project Manual is for I4C's consortium only and is made available to partners through I4C's internal communications platform on MS Teams. Contact information will be updated in the Excel file where beneficiaries' contact details are listed (I4C Master Contact Sheet.xlsx). Project execution should first and foremost follow the principles of I4C's Grant Agreement (GA), and next the Consortium Agreement (CA). This Project Manual does not replace I4C'S GA, CA or any EU guidelines for project implementation. In this document, references have been made to the GA or the CA where appropriate. Although I4C will have a Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (CDE Plan), this Project Manual also contains guidelines on how to acknowledge EC funding during dissemination and

communication activities. Data management will be outlined in a separate document (Deliverable 8.5), due M6, as well as updated versions (D8.9 due M24, and D8.10 due M36).

4 General project information

Table 2: Project details

Title	Impetus4Change: Improving Near-Term Climate Predictions For Societal Transformation
Acronym	Impetus4Change (I4C)
Grant Agreement no	101081555
Funding Programme	Horizon Europe
Call and topic	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02 Climate sciences and responses <i>Development of high-resolution Earth system models for global and regional climate change projections</i>
Topic	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D1-02-04
Funding scheme	Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
Project start date	01.11.2022
Duration	48 months
Coordinator	Stefan Sobolowski, NORCE
Service	CINEA/C/01

Table 2: I4C Consortium

PARTICIPANT NO.	PARTICIPANT ORGANISATION NAME	PARTICIPANT SHORT NAME	COUNTRY	NATURE ^a
1 (Coordinator)	NORCE NORWEGIAN RESEARCH CENTRE AS	NORCE	NO	RTO
2 (Beneficiary)	UNIVERSITY OF BERGEN	UiB	NO	UNIV
3 (Beneficiary)	HELMHOLTZ-ZENTRUM HEREON GMBH	HEREON	DE	RTO
4.1 (Beneficiary)	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS, CERFACS	CNRS-CERFACS	FR	RTO
4.2 (Beneficiary)	CENTRE NATIONAL DE LA RECHERCHE SCIENTIFIQUE CNRS, METEO-FRANCE	CNRS-MF	FR	RTO
5 (Beneficiary)	BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTER-CENTRO NACIONAL DE SUPERCOMPUTACION	BSC CNS	SP	RTO
6 (Beneficiary)	AGENCIA ESTATAL CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTIFICAS	CSIC	SP	RTO
7 (Beneficiary)	NORSK REGNESENTRAL	NRS	NO	RTO
8 (Beneficiary)	STIFTELSEN NANSEN SENTER FOR MILJO OG FJERNMALING	NERSC	NO	RTO
9 (Beneficiary)	DANMARKS METEOROLOGISKE INSTITUT	DMI	DK	RTO
10 (Beneficiary)	UNITED NATIONS EDUCATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND CULTURAL ORGANIZATION - ORGANISATION DES NATIONS UNIES POUR L'EDUCATION LA SCIENCE ET LA CULTURE	ICTP	FR	RTO
11 (Beneficiary)	MAX-PLANCK-GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER WISSENSCHAFTEN EV	MPI-M	DE	RTO
12 (Beneficiary)	ARCTIK SRL	ARCTIK	BE	SME
13 (Beneficiary)	UNIVERZITA KARLOVA	CU	CZ	UNIV
14 (Beneficiary)	LEUPHANA UNIVERSITAT LUNEBURG	LEUPHANA	DE	UNIV
15 (Beneficiary)	TRESCIENTOSMILKILOMETROSPORSEGUNDO S.L.	300K	SP	SME
16 (Beneficiary)	ICLEI EUROPEAN SECRETARIAT GMBH (ICLEI EUROPASEKRETARIAT GMBH)	ICLEI EURO	DE	RTO
17 (Associated Partner)	UNIVERSITY OF NEWCASTLE UPON TYNE	UNEW	UK	UNIV
Informal Partner	UNIVERSITY CORPORATION FOR ATMOSPHERIC RESEARCH NONPROFIT CORPORATION (National Center for Atmospheric Research)	UCAR/NCAR	USA	RTO
Informal Partner	TEXAS A&M UNIVERSITY SYSTEM	TAMU	USA	UNIV
Informal Partner	ACADEMICA SINICA	AS-RCEC	Taiwan	UNIV

^{a)} RTO: Research and Technology Organisation; UNIV: University; SME: Small and Medium Enterprise (up to 249 employees);

LE: Large Enterprise (250 or more employees)

5 Work Breakdown

Below is an overview of the work packages, deliverables, planned effort, and milestones. Further details and full work package descriptions, including tasks and objectives, can be found in Annex 1 – DoA (Annex 1 - DoA (Description of Action) from GrantAgreement-101081555-Impetus4Change.pdf). For an overview of the deliverables, milestones, and reporting periods as they occur per calendar year, please refer to Annex 1.

Table 3: Work Packages

#	Work Package Name	Lead	Effort (Person-Months)	Start Month	End Month
WP1	Knowledge networks towards societal transformation	1 - NORCE	153.00	1	48
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D1.1 – Paper reviewing the landscape of knowledge networks for adaptation in Europe D1.2 – Report on the I4C knowledge networks and their role in climate change adaptation D1.3 – Paper on the barriers and opportunities for innovative/bottom-up KN for adaptation operating in Europe D1.4 – Report on the potential to scaling out the I4C demonstrator findings within knowledge networks 				
WP2	Improving S2D predictions	2 - UiB	231.00	1	48
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D2.1 – Report on the impact of model errors and signal to noise problem on the predictive skill of decadal forecast systems D2.2 – Report on the initial evaluation of the new S2D systems D2.3 – Synthesis report on the new set of improved climate predictions 				
WP3	Regionalization of climate predictions	6 - CSIC	217.00	1	48
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D3.1 – Results and preliminary data of adjustment and downscaling activities D3.2 – Experimental protocol for the new CPRCM I4C simulations and lists of the planned runs D3.3 – Report on the CPRCM emulator development over Europe and the Demonstrators. D3.4 – Description of the Data Reference syntax for archiving results of statistical and emulation-based downscaling 				
WP4	Near-term hazard assessment	8 - NERSC	90.20	1	48
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D4.1 – Table, definitions, and descriptions of key Hazard indicators on which to focus in subsequent Tasks D4.2 – Report on assessment of hazards over Europe D4.3 – Report on the TOE of the hazard indicators D4.4 – Web-based tool to deliver region specific hazard information 				
WP5	Blending forecasts across timescales	9 - DMI	70.00	1	42
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D5.1 – Guidelines for the blending methods D5.2 – Synthesis report documenting the new I4C blending strategies D5.3 – Assessment report on all I4C blending strategies 				
WP6	Co-production of I4C Demonstrators	5 - BSC CNS	212.80	1	48
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> D6.1 – Stakeholder mapping summary report D6.2 – Status report and results of the demonstrator’s co-design process D6.3 – Report on climate services implementation and adaption support guidance pack for each demonstrator D6.4 – Co-evaluation of the Demonstrators and the co-production process D6.5 – Adapting to urban climate futures, I4C Roadmap 				

WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication	12 - ARCTIK	72.00	1	48
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D7.1 – Communication, and dissemination strategy • D7.2 – Interim report on communication and dissemination activities • D7.3 – Final report on communication and dissemination activities • D7.4 – Exploitation plan • D7.5 – Interim report on exploitation activities • D7.6 – Final report on exploitation activities • D7.7 – First update of the D&C plan • D7.8 – Second update of the D&C plan • D7.9 – Final exploitation plan 					
WP8	Project management	1 - NORCE	58.00	1	48
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • D8.1 – Management structures & procedures • D8.2 – Quality assurance protocols established (KPIs) • D8.3 – First report on quality assurance KPIs • D8.4 – Second report on quality assurance KPIs • D8.5 – Data management plan, informed consent forms & info sheets • D8.6 – Establishment of clustering activities • D8.7 – Interim report on clustering activities • D8.8 – Final report of clustering activities • D8.9 – First update of the DMP • D8.10 – Second update of the DMP 					

Table 4: Staff effort per participant

Participant	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	Total Person-Months
1 - NORCE	60		16			31	7	47	161
2 - UiB		36	12						48
3 - Hereon-GERICS	8		24			16			48
4 - CNRS		20	45		10	35			110
4.1 - CERFACS		10	1		2				13
4.2 - METEO-FRANCE			8			1		1	10
5 - BSC CNS	60	42	12		20	60	4	6	204
6 - CSIC			44		12		24	4	84
7 - NRS				8	10				18
8 - NERSC		27		28					55
9 - DMI		18	14	6	16				54
10 - UNESCO-ICTP			24	28					52
11 - MPI-M		36							36
12 - ARCTIK							37		37
13 - CU			3			40			43
14 - LEUPHANA	17					6.4			23.4
15 - 300K						8			8
16 - ICLEI Europe	8								8
17 - AS		28							28
18 - UCAR		10	4						14
19 - UNEW				20.2		15.4			35.6
20 - TAMU		4	10						14

Total Person-Months	153	231	217	90.2	70	212.8	72	58	1 104
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Table 5: Milestones

#	Milestone Name	Work Package No	Lead	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)
1	Initial demonstrator co-exploration meetings	6 7 8	4-CNRS	Photos summary on website	6
2	First Klimathon	1 6 7	12-ARCTIK	Photo(s) article summary on website social media posts	18
3	Expert selected subset of bias- and drift-corrected baseline predictions provided to WP3	2 3	2-UiB	Data paths shared + acknowledged in GA meeting minutes	18
4	Mini-workshop (during yr. 2 GA) on final Demonstrator mock-ups including explicit links to WPs2-5	1-6	5-BSC CNS	Minutes of GA meeting discussion	18
5	Summary of T1.2. survey questions rationale and dissemination	1 6 7	1-NORCE	Internal review	20
6	Adjusted/downscaled data ready for WP4 and WP6; Data from the CPRCM simulations are available for Task3.3 WP4 and WP6	3 4 6	6-CSIC	Data/internal report	27
7	Estimation of extreme events based on existing datasets.	4	8-NERSC	Data/internal report.	27
8	Selection of case studies to assess the utility of the blended products in WP5	5	9-DMI	Internal report	27
9	Computation of the TOE for selected extremes and hazards; estimation of extreme and hazard climate change projections at the selected tipping points.	4	8-NERSC	Internal report	30
10	Protocol for coordinated experiments with improved decadal predictions systems	2	2-UiB	Internal report	32
11	Production of large ensembles of emulator-based regionalized decadal predictions for WP4 and WP6	3	6-CSIC	Internal report	33
12	Events presenting the demonstrator outputs in each city	6	5-BSC CNS	Articles/ Summaries published on project website and promoted on social media vlog from event	33
13	Delivery of blended information for the Demonstrators in WP6	5	9-DMI	Blended data uploaded and documented in I4C EUDAT	36

14	Identify criteria for pursuing the review of the literature on the KN	1	1-NORCE	Internal review	43
15	EOSC open science tools launched and final version of the open tools posted to GitHub	7	12-ARCTIK	Press release and portal open and accessible software available in Git repository	44
16	S2D Model output released	2	2-UiB	Model output DOI	48
17	Large ensemble Emulator data released	7	6-CSIC	Data DOI	48
18	Discuss and finalise choice of data indices and GWLs during the GA for extremes assessment	4 6	10- UNESCO- ICTP	Minutes of GA meeting	18

6 Legal basis

All partners must be familiar with the legal documents regulating project implementation, the GA and the CA. For detailed explanations and examples of articles in the GA, consult the [Annotated Model Grant Agreement \(AMGA\)](#) and [Horizon Europe online manual](#).

6.1 Grant Agreement

I4C's GA takes precedence above all other documents concerning the project. It is organised with the following parts:

- Terms and Conditions (core contract)
- Annex 1 Description of the Action (DoA)
- Annex 2 Estimated budget for the action
- Annex 3 Accession Forms
- Annex 4 Model for the financial statements
- Annex 5 Model for the CFS
- Annex 6 Model for the certificate on the methodology

The GA is signed by the Coordinator and the EC, and all beneficiaries became parties to the GA by signing the online Accession Forms. All partners must keep a copy on file and provide it to auditors, if necessary. The GA can be found on I4C's Teams Site ([GrantAgreement-101081555-Impetus4Change_102022.pdf](#), accessible to the consortium members, or it can be downloaded from I4C's project area in EU's funding and tender portal.

Annex 1. Description of the Action (DoA), details how the project will be carried out. It consists of two parts, part A and B, derived from the submitted proposal and revised during the GA preparation stage:

Part A: Cover page, project summary, list of participants and work plan tables (WPs description, Deliverables and Milestones) with details on project implementation.

Part B: Is the narrative part of I4C’s DoA and is an updated version of the proposal with the sections: excellence, impact, implementation, members of the consortium, ethics and security. From the project start, it is important to only use the GA for correct information on the project, and not the submitted proposal.

6.2 Consortium Agreement

The CA allows consortium members to agree on any specific details not covered by the GA, such as the organisation of work, intellectual property management, conflict resolution, liability, and future exploitation and dissemination of results. The agreement itself details parties’ rights and obligations and is signed between all beneficiaries. All partners must keep a copy of CA on file and provide it to auditors, if necessary. This document can also be found in I4C’s MS 365 Teams (Consortium Agreement_Impetus4Change_final_signed.pdf).

7 I4C Management Structure and Procedures

In this section, the governing bodies of the Project I4C and the main roles of the various partners within the project’s management structure are described. I4C has the following consortium bodies:

- General Assembly
- Scientific Steering Committee (SSC)
- Demonstrator Task Team (DTT)
- Clustering Activities Task Team
- Data Management Panel

Figure 1: Overview of I4C’s management structure

I4C also has the following key roles:

- Project Office (PO): NORCE (PC, PM, FM)
- Project Lead Coordinator (PC): Stefan Sobolowski
- Project co-Coordinator: Dragana Bojovic (BSC)
- Project Manager (PM) (administrative management): Megan Brunswig
- Financial Manager (FM) (budgetary management): Mona Horvei
- Work Package (WP) Leaders: See I4C Master Contact Sheet.xlsx
- Task Leaders (TL): See I4C Master Contact Sheet.xlsx
- Data Manager (DM): Ozan Mert Göktürk (NORCE)

7.1 Key Consortium Bodies

7.1.1 General Assembly (GA)

Purpose	The GA represents the highest level of decision-making within the project, and it will decide the overall project strategy (e.g., contractual matters, exploitation issues).
Chair	PC (NORCE)
Members	One primary and one secondary representative from each partner; members have decision-making authority from their own institutions for the purposes of the project (see Table 6)
Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluate technical and scientific progress on the basis of reports given by the SSC and decide on the project strategy and schedule, propose changes or new procedures; • Act upon proposals from the SSC; • Study the progress and EC review reports on all partners' activities; • Solve conflicts on issues impacting strategies, medium/long term objectives, resources and the project roll-out strategies; • Coordinate common exploitation and dissemination actions; • By confidential vote; decide on financial allocation, entering new contractors, review or amend EU contract, change or exchange of work packages. Contract changes (tasks, budgets, partners) require votes; • Prepare eventual contract changes (budget, resources, plans, etc.).
Meeting Frequency	The GA will meet at least every 12 months, usually in conjunction with the Annual Meeting. Extraordinary meetings may occur at any time upon request of the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC) or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly

Table 6: General Assembly Members as of January 2023**Beneficiaries:**

Participant	Primary Representative	Secondary Representative
NORCE	Stefan Sobolowski	Megan Brunswig
UiB	Noel Keenlyside	TBC
Hereon-GERICS	Claas Teichmann	Gaby Lagendijk
CNRS-CERFACS	Julien Boé	Emilia Sanchez-Gomez
CNRS-MF	Samuel Somot	Aude Lemonsu
BSC	Dragana Bojovic	Pablo Ortega
CSIC	Jesús Fernández	José Manuel Gutiérrez
NRS	Alex Lenkoski	Thea Roksvåg
NERSC	Francois Counillon	Stephen Outten
DMI	Shuting Yang	Ole Bøssing Christensen
ICTP	Erika Coppola	TBC
MPI-M	Daniela Matei	TBC
ARCTIK	Anya Gregory	TBC
CU	Tomas Halenka	TBC
LU	Astrid Kause	TBC
300K	Mar Santamaria	Pablo Martinez
ICLEI- Europe	Vasileios Latinos	Maria von Mach

Associated Partners (no voting on financial matters):

UNEW	Hayley Fowler	TBC
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7.1.2 Scientific Steering Committee (SSC)

Purpose	The SSC is the most important scientific body of I4C. The SSC will monitor and control scientific project strategy, including, for example, verifying achieved objectives, control deviations, apply contingency measures and establish corrective actions. Every suggestion, conclusion and agreement by the SSC will be communicated to the GA, and if required, discussed and approved in a GA Meeting.
Chair	PC (NORCE)
Members	Work Package Leaders (see Table 7)
Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Control and monitor the scientific work; · Take decisions about the scientific and technical schedule of the project; · Monitor and report on the project's Key Performance Indicators and ensure progress towards the project's deliverables; · Ensure technical planning and coherence of results; · Generate reports of technical and scientific progress at PO's request · Report to the GA and consult with them as necessary in the event of changes to the work plan, financial or any other relevant issues; · Execute decisions approved by the GA;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Field reports from the DTT and take decisions regarding the progress of the Demonstrators, monitor stakeholder engagement and proactively address and stakeholder related issues; Report on the progress of I4C and organize input from the EC.
Meeting Frequency	<p>The SSC will meet at least every 6 months.</p> <p>Additional meetings may occur at any time upon request of any Member of the Scientific Steering Committee (SSC)</p>

The project manager will be an ex-officio member and an ECS representative will be approved by the GA.

Table 7: SSC Members as of January 2023

Role	Names	Organisation
PC & WP8 lead	Stefan Sobolowski	NORCE
PM*	Megan Brunswig	NORCE
PF*	Mona Horvei	NORCE
WP1 lead	Marta Bruno Soares (Ivan Gonzalez)	NORCE
WP2 lead	Noel Keenlyside (Emilia Sanchez)	UiB (CNRS)
WP3 lead	José Manuel Gutiérrez (Samuel Somot)	CSIC (CNRS MF)
WP4 lead	Stephen Outten (Erika Coppola)	NERSC (ICTP)
WP5 lead	Shuting Yang (Pablo Ortega Montilla)	DMI (BSC)
WP6 lead	Dragana Bojovic (Gaby Langendijk)	BSC (Hereon-GERICS)
WP7 lead	Anya Gregory	ARCTIK

* Non-voting roles in committee (observer)

Additional People Attending the SSC Meetings:

- Gaby Langendijk (HEREON (GERICS))
- Julien Boé (CNRS-CECI (CERFACS))

7.1.3 Demonstrator Task Team (DTT)

We define a body called the “Demonstrator Task Team” (DTT), members of which are to be selected from among the demonstrator cities in WP6 (one per demonstrator) as well as one representative from WP1. We will aim to have 50% of this team selected from ECSs in the project. This team will have general responsibility to ensure the smooth operation of the Demonstrators, stakeholder engagement and for the exploitation synergies between Demonstrators. The DTT will report to the Scientific Steering Committee of the project. At the in-person kick off

meeting Trieste Italy (24-26, January 2023) the task team had its first meeting. Gaby Langendijk and Mathew Stiller-Reeve offered to co-lead the task team and members of the task team were selected from the demonstrators and relevant work packages.

Participants Demonstrator Task Team:

Role	Names	Organisation
Lead	Gaby Langendijk	Hereon-GERICS
Co-Lead	Mathew Stiller-Reeve	Konsulent Stiller-Reeve
WP1	Marta Bruno Soares Astrid	NORCE
WP2	Noel Keenlyside (TBC)	UiB
WP3	Antoine Doury	CNRS-MF
WP4	Hayley Fowler Erika Coppola	UNEW ICTP
WP5	Shuting Yang	DMI
WP6	Dragana Bojovic	BSC
WP7	Anya Gregory	ARCTIK
Barcelona Demo	Dragana Bojovic	BSC
Bergen Demo	Lu Li Stephanie Mayer	NORCE NORCE
Paris Demo	Aude Lemonsu Valery Masson	CNRS-MF CNRS-MF
Prague Demo	Tomas Halenka	CU

7.1.4 Data Management Panel

Data and tools management is a critical part of I4C, both from an exploitation perspective as well as a matter of ensuring efficient data sharing and synchronisation between different work packages and tasks. Ozan Mert Göktürk has been designated data manager of the project and will lead the data and tools management panel.

Representatives from each of the technical work packages were selected to the panel at the in-person kick off in Trieste Italy (24-26, January 2023). The panel will be responsible for I4Cs DMP and will contribute to the development of I4C's exploitation plan, which will heavily feature open science tools and access (e.g., liaising with, and ensuring exploitation through, the European Open Science Cloud).

Participants Data Management Panel:

Role	Names	Organisation
Lead	Ozan Mert Göktürk	NORCE
WP1	Ivan Puga-Gonzalez	NORCE
WP2	Marie-Pierre Moine	CERFACS
WP3	Ole Christensen	DMI
WP4	Alex Lenkoski	NR
WP5	Marie-Pierre Moine	CERFACS
WP6	Claas Teichmann	Hereon-GERICS
WP7	TBC	TBC

7.1.5 Clustering Activities Task Team

Clustering activities with our sister project, ASPECT and other relevant projects and initiatives is critical to ensure broad communication and dissemination of project results. Clustering will also help up to exploit multipliers and take advantage of collaboration activities. Since this is a high-level activity, Stefan Sobolowski (lead scientific coordinator) and Anya Gregory (CDE WP lead) are leading this task team. The team had its first meeting at the in-person kick off in Trieste Italy (24-26, January 2023) and will take regular meetings with the leadership of ASPECT in order best take advantage of clustering activities.

7.2 Key roles**7.2.1 Project Coordinator Office (PO)**

Responsible (NORCE)	Stefan Sobolowski Megan Brunswig Mona Horvei
CoLead (BSC)	Dragana Bojovic
Role	The PO is the intermediary between the participants and CINEA the Granting Authority. The PO performs all tasks assigned to it as described in the GA and in the CA.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Monitoring compliance by the Participants with their obligations under the CA and the GA; - Overall project administrative management and coordination; - Consolidate progress reports once PC has checked/reviewed them; - Collect, compose and send progress reports on all activities per partner and per WPLs for each period; - Execute and oversee general project policies in the Consortium; - Analyse potential and real conflicts between partners and propose agreements; - Trace and correct deviations to the work programme, helped by PC, especially through follow-up of identified critical paths; - Organise and prepare Consortium Body meetings as per the schedule or when necessary;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, deliverables (incl. financial statements and certifications) and other requested documents to the Granting Authority CINEA; - Transmitting I4C related information and documents to the Participants concerned; - Fulfilling financial tasks (CA, Section 7.2); - Administering financial contribution of the Granting Authority; - Keep address lists updated and available.
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7.2.1.1 Project Coordinator

Responsible	Stefan Sobolowski
Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Overall responsibility for the project I4C - Responsible for the overall scientific progress of I4C, quality of the results and timely submission of all required documents and reports to the EC
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Steering the coordination & management team - Ensuring that the action is implemented properly - Leading and managing all scientific aspects of I4C - Supervising research data policy - Managing risk and ethical issues in I4C - Promoting I4C at scientific and other meetings to ensure the sustainability of project results and successful dissemination - Ensuring effective collaboration and efficient flow of information in I4C - Identifying and building synergies between relevant H2020/HEU projects and other European funded projects - Approving financial reporting and monitoring I4C's finances

7.2.1.2 Project Manager (PM)

Responsible	Megan Brunswig
Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Administrative management is delegated from PC manager to the PM. - Involves coordinating the operational, administrative and management activities of the project. - The Project manager will generally provide the 'back office' services required for successful project completion and will support the PC in the overall coordination of the project.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Daily support of the overall coordination and management of I4C activities, ensuring that the project is delivered on time and to budget - Day-to-day management of I4C in the EC Grant Management system - Supporting the PC in planning and reviewing the deliverables and outcomes to ensure their timely delivery - Setting-up and update the administrative and management procedures of I4C - Providing management tools (e.g. guides, templates, address list, online collaboration environment etc.) - Informing and advising participants on financial and administrative rules, while ensuring the conformity with the relevant procedures

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Organisation of, support to and participation in, where relevant, the meetings of the Consortium bodies. Including meeting minutes. - Monitoring all contractual obligations, including transmittance of documents and information connected with I4C to any other participant and administrative additional agreements. - Primary responsibility for updating the information on the European Commission's platform. - Overview of the project budget in collaboration with the PC
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7.2.1.3 Financial Manager (FM)

Responsible	Mona Horvei
Role	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The financial project officer will assure that the project fulfils the financial requirements and that the economic dispositions are in line with the EC financial rules.
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Financial contact person for the partners financial officers. - Managing payments from the EU to the consortium according to the CA - Implementing budget changes on behalf of the consortium - Financial reporting and information to partners in this regard - Entering and updating the financial information in the EU portal

7.2.1.4 Work package leaders and co-leads

Responsible	WP Leads/co-leads (see SSC Table)
Role	Coordination of Work Packages and with PC (co-leads to support and step in if leads are unavailable)
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Coordinate, plan and monitor activities within their respective work package; - Identify critical WP implementation risks and mitigation actions, and alerting the PC of deviations to the work plan; - Ensure technical planning and coherence of WP results; - Generate WP reports of technical and scientific progress on PM's request and follow up decisions made by Consortium bodies; - Assess quality of deliverables before sent for internal reviews.

7.2.1.5 Task Leaders

Responsible	Task Leads (see Master Contact Sheet)
Role	Coordination of the technical work, and making day-to-day technical decisions affecting their task, in close communication with the respective WPL
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Planning and monitoring activities and deliverables within their respective tasks; - Reporting progress on the corresponding WPL's request.

Responsible	Ozan Mert Göktürk (NORCE)
Role	Planning of DMP and oversight of its implementation
Responsibilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Develop Data Management Plan in cooperation with PC and SSC, and EC requirements - Ensure project participants follow the DMP - Establish and follow up on the project's exploitation plan

7.3 Communications within I4C's consortium

7.3.1 Meetings

Below is a description of meetings planned in I4C that are not already described above. Some are intended to be physical meetings, others digital. If necessary (i.e., due to Covid or other challenges), in person meetings will be held virtually in order to avoid delays.

Annual Meetings for the Consortium:

I4C's consortium meets annually throughout the duration of the project and will be organized in conjunction with annual GA meetings (see below). Locations are to be determined by the SSC. The PC is responsible for the agenda, and minutes together with the local organisers. Participants book their own flights and accommodation and are responsible for these costs.

Review meetings: Three review meetings are expected during project lifetime following the submission of the M18, M36 and M48 periodic reports. In the review meetings, the SSC meets with the REA/EC and the reviewer appointed by the EC. The PC and WPLs present progress of the project and answer the questions from external evaluators and representatives from REA/EC. These meetings will most likely take place in Brussels, or online.

WP and Task meetings: WPL and TLs organize meetings at a frequency necessary for project implementation to follow the planned progression. The WPL or TL is responsible for the agenda and minutes. It is recommended to have WP meetings monthly.

7.3.2 Folder Structure

File sharing for I4C is set up via Teams/Sharepoint. If you do not have access to the Team site, please contact the PM (email). All information housed on the Team site should be treated as consortium confidential unless stated otherwise.

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- Link to I4C folders in Team
- Link to same folders via Sharepoint. (Team's folder structure is based on and linked to Sharepoint)

There should be an option to sync Teams/Sharepoint folders with OneDrive for example such that you can access the folders directly from your file structure rather than signing into the Teams platform each time. Guidance to do this can be found [here](#).

Where to find things:

Each work package has its own folder with folders for each deliverable and meetings. Work packages are of course free to add whatever additional folders they wish to have. Though you may of course have your own personal folders elsewhere, we ask that as a minimum all key documentation for the deliverables, etc. is maintained in these folders.

Under WP 8 (Project Management) you will find, among other things:

- Copies of the Consortium Agreement, Grant Agreement (with Description of Action, final budget, etc.)
- periodic and internal reporting templates
- minutes from the Annual Meetings, Scientific Steering Committee, etc.
- Communications templates and profile/branding items

In addition, a workspace has been established on Mattermost, which is a Slack-like workflow enhancement tool. The workspace enables fast and seamless communication and links to commonly used software repositories such as GitHub. The workspace is managed by I4C GA member Claas Teichmann and is owned by I4C partner Hereon-GERICS.

7.3.3 Internal communication by e-mail

A major part of project communication is expected to take place via e-mails. As many participants are connected to a variety of projects, **we strongly encourage you to start all subject lines with "I4C: "**

The I4C Master Contact Sheet.xlsx is a living document providing an overview of all participants in the consortium and their respective roles. It will be updated to reflect any changes in personnel, responsibilities, contact details, etc. It is the responsibility of each partner to notify the PM in order to keep this file up to date. The main partner contact sends an e-mail notification to the PM, with cc to the person(s) to be added or removed, and relevant WPLs. I4C's PM will then update contact list, Teams access and e-mail groups. WPLs will update recurring meetings in order to include/exclude persons added/removed.

In general:

- When sending queries to the coordinating institution (NORCE), address Stefan Sobolowski for scientific issues (email), Megan Brunswig (email) for administrative issues, and Mona Horvei (email) for finance issues.
- I4C-PMO @ norceresearch.no can be used to reach all three PO contacts at once.

- Remember to send a copy to the PC (email) in important e-mail correspondences.

8 Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

8.1 Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plans

I4C will develop a Communication and dissemination strategy, with a first draft at M6 (deliverable 7.1) and subsequent updates at M24 (deliverable 7.2), and M47 (deliverable 7.3). In addition, an Exploitation plan will also be developed at the same intervals (deliverables 7.4-6). Beneficiaries should consult these plans for dissemination and external communication. Beneficiaries should notify the WP7 leader for upfront reporting of and post-involvement in dissemination and communications events for I4C. All CDE activities must be registered in the tracking-file on Teams (coming soon). This information will be used both for further dissemination/communication on relevant platforms like I4C's web pages and social media accounts, and as part of the PC's continuous reporting obligations of dissemination and communication events in EU's funding and tender portal.

NORCE will be responsible for issuing a bi-monthly internal newsletter that provides an update of internal project matters, such as updates to key personnel, upcoming deliverables, clarifications on procedures, upcoming events of interest, etc.

Arctik will be responsible for an external newsletter, which will promote on the project's profile, and highlight project activities and interests.

All partners are responsible for updating Arctik and the PC/PM for items of relevance for the newsletters and CDE activities in general.

8.2 Open access to scientific publications

Each beneficiary must ensure gold or green open access (free of charge, online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results, according to GA article 29. Differences of gold or green open access are found here: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm

8.3 Obligation to disseminate results

An important part of achieving expected impact in an EU-project is that beneficiaries, as soon as possible, disseminate its results by disclosing them to the public unless this goes against their legitimate interests. Obligations to disseminate results are further outlined in GA Article 17 and the GA Specific Rules (Annex 5) and CA 8.4.2.1.

8.4 Compulsory acknowledgement

Projects receiving funding from the EU are required to acknowledge it by using the following procedure (see Article 29 in GA):

1. Display the EU emblem (when displayed together with another logo, the EU emblem must have appropriate prominence):

2. Include the following text: *“Funded by the European Union”*
3. According to Article 29.5 in GA; “Any dissemination of results must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”

[Further Guidance](#)

4. Include the project logo:

Other profile info can be found on I4C's Teams area (Branding).

9 Reporting

Within I4C, several types of reporting are required:

- Continuous reporting to PC, WPLs and/or TL
- [Continuous reporting via EU portal](#), including deliverables and milestones
- [Internal reporting](#): brief financial reporting at months 9, 27, and 42 to the PC/PM/FM.
- [Periodical reporting](#): comprehensive technical and financial reporting after M18, M36, and M48 to the EC

- Final report after M48, for the entire project duration, to the EC.

Several templates are being generated for I4C (file type in parenthesis):

- Deliverables (.doc)
- Milestone notification (.doc)
- Financial Internal Reporting (.doc)

These templates can be found in the WP8 Project Management folder, in the “Templates” folder under EC Reporting and Internal Reporting respectively.

Beneficiaries should familiarise themselves with the content and requests of EU’s funding and tender portal.

9.1 Continuous reporting

The continuous reporting follows the project progress through the submission of:

1. Deliverables;
2. Achievement of milestones;
3. List of publications; and
4. Communication and dissemination tracking.

A complete list of milestones and deliverables for I4C are available in the Grant Agreement, in the EU funding and tender portal, and in the appendices of this manual.

9.1.1 Approval process of deliverables

To ensure submission of timely and high-quality deliverables, I4C will establish a routine that will be discussed further with the SSC.

Planned process:

- Upcoming deliverables noted in internal newsletters.
- Reminders sent out by PM 4 weeks prior to deadline to responsible partner including the deliverable template.
- Another reminder/check sent out by PM 2 weeks prior to deadline.
- Deliverable responsible to submit a near-final draft to PC-PM 1 week prior to deadline.
- PC uploads the agreed and finalised deliverable on the participant portal in time for submission deadline.

Guiding Points for Quality:

- Be concise. Deliverable reports should be to the point, and do not need to go into extensive scientific detail. The purpose of the deliverables is to demonstrate that the project is achieving its goals and is on-track with the planned timeline.
- Use the template. Deliverable templates are available with relevant/necessary sections included as guidelines for what should be included.

The deliverable leader will be appointed by the responsible institution, and will be the responsible editor for the deliverable. This person is responsible for collecting input from all partners (co-authors) as necessary to fulfil its objective. To ensure high quality of all project deliverables I4C implements a process for internal quality assurance before submission to the EC.

A review of the deliverable will examine that:

- The deliverable is consistent with the objectives and contain all expected information to satisfy the deliverable requirements as outlined in the GA
- The deliverable is a basis for continued work and interdependent deliverables to satisfy future requirements
- The deliverable is well-structured and described in clear text and plain language, without overloading the report with unnecessary or irrelevant information.

The deliverable leader and co-authors will revise in accordance with comments provided by the reviewers as soon as possible and share the final document with PC at least 3 days prior to the deadline.

9.1.2 Nomenclature of Deliverables

In order to keep the titling of Deliverables clear and easy to find, please use the following nomenclature when naming your files: *I4C Del# [Deliverable Title]*

9.1.3 Notification of milestones

The milestone leader will be appointed by the responsible institution, and will be the responsible editor for the deliverable.

This person fills out the milestone template and shares it with the PC at least one week prior to the deadline for submission.

The PC will update the EU’s funding and tender portal with achieved milestones.

9.2 Internal progress reports

I4C’s beneficiaries shall submit internal financial project reports, to enable monitoring of project progress. These should be short progress reports summarising spent personnel costs and direct costs.

Any deviations from plans (budget and content), according to the Annex 2, shall be explained. Progress reports from partners shall be submitted to the PC, where any deviations may be cross-checked with WPLs, if necessary. Templates for the internal reporting are available in the I4C Teams folder (see above).

9.3 Periodic reporting

Periodic report(s) to the EC, to demonstrate progress and to release interim and final payments, is due from the I4C's consortium M18, M36 and M48 (see GA: Article 21.2). These reports are composed of the periodic technical and financial reports and must be submitted by the PC within 60 days following the end of each reporting period, through the EC portal.

9.3.1 Internal routine for periodic reporting in I4C

Each beneficiary should complete their own Financial Statement (and the financial report of their Third Parties, if any) filling in the on-line form **no later than 30 days after the end of each reporting period**, including explanations on use of resources. Each beneficiary (and each linked third party) must certify that information provided is full, reliable and true; that declared costs are eligible (see GA Article 6), and can be substantiated by adequate records and supporting documentation (see GA Article 20) that will be produced upon request by the EC (see GA Article 19). Beneficiaries Financial Statement must be signed electronically by beneficiary's PFSIGN.

The periodic technical report will be 'locked for review' by the PC before its submission.

Note that, if an individual financial statement is not submitted for a reporting period, it may be included in the periodic financial report for the next reporting period.

An example of the periodic [reporting templates for Horizon Europe can be found here](#).

Pending approval by the EC, interim payments will be received within 90 days after submitting the periodic report. Approval is dependent on the acceptance of the technical and financial reports, reviewed by the EC using external reviewers. The SSC participate in review meetings with the Commission, to take place within the 90 days mentioned above.

9.4 Final report

In addition to the periodic report for the final reporting period (M48), the PC must submit a final report (see GA: Article 21.2) within 60 days following the end of reporting period. I4C will follow the same internal routine as for periodic reporting. Beneficiaries requesting a contribution of more than 430 000 EUR EU contribution (direct cost plus 25%

indirect costs) need to submit a CFS, detailed in GA Article 20.3, as a scanned copy (PDF) together with the financial statement for the final reporting period. Beneficiaries must keep the signed original in their files. The certificate must be issued by an external auditor, using Annex 5 of I4C's GA.

9.5 Keeping records - supporting documentation

Each beneficiary must for a period of five years after the payment of the balance keep records and other supporting documentation in order to prove the proper implementation of the action and the costs they declare as eligible (see Special Rules, Annex 5 of the GA and Article 18) and make them available upon request (see GA Article 20) or in the context of checks, reviews, audits or investigations (see GA Article 25).

9.5.1 Time recording

For personnel costs (declared as actual costs or on the basis of unit costs), beneficiaries must keep time records for number of hours declared. The time recording can be done by using a timesheet on paper or in a computer-based system. For more information on time recording including a list of minimum requirements see GA article 18. An example template for a timesheet, provided by the EC, can be found [here](#).

Information included in timesheets must match records of annual leave, sick leave, other leaves and work-related travel. The time sheet template provided is not mandatory; beneficiaries may use their own model, provided that it fulfils the minimum conditions, and it contains at least the information detailed in GA.

9.6 Reporting calendar

I4C have internal progress reports from the beneficiaries to the PC every 6 months, apart from when there is periodic reporting to the EC. Periodic reporting to the EC is at M18, M36 and M48.

Table 7: Reporting calendar. UPDATE

Report	Period	Deadline to WPL	Deadline to PC	Finalised and submitted to EC by PC
Internal Financial Progress Report	M1-M9	n/a	M9 + 15 days	n/a
Periodic Progress Report	M1-M18	M18 + 30 days	M18 + 45 days	M18 + 60 days
Internal Financial Progress Report	M18-27	n/a	M27 + 15 days	n/a
Periodic Progress Report	M19-M36	M36 + 30 days	M36 + 45 days	M36 + 60 days
Internal Financial Progress Report	M36-42	n/a	M42+15 days	n/a
Periodic Progress Report	M36-M48	M48 + 30 days	M48 + 45 days	M48 + 60 days
Final Report	M1-M48	M48 + 30 days	M48 + 45 days	M48 + 60 days

10 Risk Assessment and Mitigation Plan for in-person interactions

Should the global pandemic impacts meetings, communications activities and generated potential delays, I4C will move all meetings to online platforms and increase the project's social media presence. Assessment of COVID impacts will be on the agenda at WP meetings and Steering Committee meetings. Where in-person interaction across beneficiaries are critical, a COVID-19 Risk Assessment and Mitigation Plan (RAMP) must be completed by the beneficiary hosting the work. A template for RAMP is available.

Table 8: Critical risks & risk management strategy

#	Description	Work Package No(s)	Proposed Mitigation Measures
1	Insufficient computational resources	5,6,7,1,2,4,3,8	The modeling centers have access to their own supercomputing resources, many of which will be provided in-kind.
2	Absence of key staff	7,6,5,1,4,2,3,8	All leadership roles have a succession plan. All WPs have lead and co-lead roles and same is true for the project coordination. At the task level PMs are spread evenly to ensure that work can continue smoothly in the event of absence.
3	Difficulty maintaining stakeholder engagement in Demonstrators	6	The participants in the Demonstrators were chosen explicitly for their long-standing relationships with I4C; contact points are set to be frequent but short and limited travel is expected of the demonstrator participants; all expenses are covered
4	Difficulty engaging with other KN (and its actors) that are not part of the consortium	1	We will use contacts we have within our consortium e.g., from UoL, BSC, ICLEI, to reach out and engage with other KN.
5	Emulators fail to provide plausible regionalized data for the other WPs.	3	Activities on state-of-the-art statistical downscaling approaches included in Task 3.1 would be strengthened to cover the needs.
6	Delays in the implementation of the blending methodologies	5	Preliminary versions of the blending methodologies will start to be developed soon before the preparation of Deliverable 5.1 and will be adjusted immediately after to take into account its main guidelines and recommendations.
7	Tight timeline to incorporate results from WPs 1-5 into the Demonstrators	6	It is unlikely that all outputs from the project will be delayed; in the event that some are, the Demonstrators are prepared to work with existing simulations and outputs and tailor their guidance accordingly
8	Low interest of researchers in supporting	5,6,7,1,2,4,3,8	Monthly reminders sent to all work package leaders to gain information to populate the website, articles, social media etc. Organization

	dissemination and communication activities		of bi- lateral meetings with other work packages on dissemination and communication activities and organizing social events around e.g., designing video blogs.
9	COVID-19 (or other) restrictions	5,7,6,1,2,4,3,8	We now have a wealth of experience working virtually and we are prepared to switch most activities to on-line formats as required. The Klimathons have been run successfully both in-person and virtually. In person solutions (outdoor venues, spacing, etc.) have also been successfully employed by project partners.

11 Appendices

11.1 Calendar of Key Reporting Dates

(Note: Dissemination level for all deliverables has been set to public.)

#	WP Del# (Milestone#)	Name	Lead	Type	Project Month	Year	Actual Month
					M1	2022	November
					M2		December
1	D8.1	Management structures & procedures	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report	M3	2023	January
					M4		February
2	D8.2	Quality assurance protocols established (KPIs)	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report	M5		March
3	D7.1	Communication, and dissemination strategy	12 - ARCTIK	DEC -Websites, patent filings, vids	M6		April
4	D7.4	Exploitation plan	1 - NORCE	DEC -Websites, patent filings, vids			
5	D8.5	Data management plan, informed consent forms & info sheets	1 - NORCE	DMP — Data Management Plan			
	(M1)	Initial demonstrator co-exploration meetings	4-CNRS	Photos, summary on website			
6	D8.6	Establishment of clustering activities	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report	M7		May
					M8		June
7	D4.1	Table, definitions, and descriptions of key Hazard indicators on which to focus in subsequent Tasks	19 - UNEW	R — Document, report	M9		July (internal reporting)
8	D6.1	Stakeholder mapping summary report	5 - BSC CNS	R — Document, report			August
					M10	September	
					M11		
9	D1.1	Paper reviewing the landscape of knowledge networks for adaptation in Europe	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report	M12	October (end yr 1)	
10	D3.2	Experimental protocol for the new CPRCM I4C simulations and lists of the planned runs	3 - Hereon	R — Document, report			
11	D5.1	Guidelines for the blending methods	9 - DMI	R — Document, report			
					M13	November	
					M14	December	
					M15	January	
					M16	February	
					M17	March	
12	D3.4	Description of the Data Reference syntax for archiving results of statistical and emulation-based downscaling	9 - DMI	R — Document, report	M18	2024	April (end 1st reporting period)

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13	D6.2	Status report and results of the demonstrator’s co-design process	4 - CNRS	R — Document, report			
	(M2)	First Klimathon	12-ARCTIK	Photo(s), article summary on website, social media posts			
	(M3)	Expert selected subset of bias- and drift-corrected baseline predictions provided to WP3	2-UiB	Data paths shared + acknowledged in GA meeting minutes			
	(M4)	Mini-workshop (during yr. 2 GA) on final Demonstrator mock-ups including explicit links to WPs2-5	5-BSC CNS	Minutes of GA meeting discussion			
	(M18)	Discuss and finalise choice of data, indices, and GWLs during the GA for extremes assessment	10-UNESCO-ICTP	Minutes of GA meeting			
					M19		May
	(M5)	Summary of T1.2. survey questions, rationale and dissemination	1-NORCE	Internal review	M20		June (1st Periodic Report Due)
					M21		July
					M22		August
					M23		September
14	D2.1	Report on the impact of model errors and signal to noise problem on the predictive skill of decadal forecast systems	11 - MPI-M	R — Document, report			
15	D7.2	Interim report on communication and dissemination activities	12 - ARCTIK	DEC -Websites, patent filings, vids			
16	D7.5	Interim report on exploitation activities	6 - CSIC	R — Document, report	M24		October (end Yr 2)
17	D7.7	First update of the D&C plan	12 - ARCTIK	R — Document, report			
18	D8.7	Interim report on clustering activities	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report			
19	D8.9	First update of the DMP	1 - NORCE	DMP — Data Management Plan			
20	D8.3	First report on quality assurance KPIs	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report	M25		November
					M26		December
	(M6)	Adjusted/downscaled data ready for WP4 and WP6; Data from the CPRCM simulations are available for Task3.3, WP4 and WP6	6-CSIC	Data/internal report			
	(M7)	Estimation of extreme events based on existing datasets.	8-NERSC	Data/internal report.	M27		January (internal reporting)
	(M8)	Selection of case studies to assess the utility of the blended products in WP5	9-DMI	Internal report		2025	
					M28		February
					M29		March
21	D5.2	Synthesis report documenting the new I4C blending strategies	4 - CNRS	R — Document, report			
	(M9)	Computation of the TOE for selected extremes and hazards; estimation of extreme and hazard climate change	8-NERSC	Internal report	M30		April

		projections at the selected tipping points.					
					M31		May
22	D1.2	Report on the I4C knowledge networks and their role in climate change adaptation	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report	M32		June
	(M10)	Protocol for coordinated experiments with improved decadal predictions systems	2-UiB	Internal report			
	(M11)	Production of large ensembles of emulator-based regionalized decadal predictions for WP4 and WP6	6-CSIC	Internal report	M33		July
	(M12)	Events presenting the demonstrator outputs in each city	5-BSC CNS	Articles/Summaries published on project website and promoted on social media, vlog from event			
23	D1.3	Paper on the barriers and opportunities for innovative/bottom-up KN for adaptation operating in Europe	5 - BSC CNS	R — Document, report	M34		August
					M35		September
24	D2.2	Report on the initial evaluation of the new S2D systems	5 - BSC CNS	R — Document, report	M36		October (end Yr 3) end 2nd reporting period
25	D3.1	Results and preliminary data of adjustment and downscaling activities	6 - CSIC	DATA — data sets, microdata, etc			
26	D7.8	Second update of the D&C plan	12 - ARCTIK	R — Document, report			
27	D8.10	Second update of the DMP	1 - NORCE	DMP — Data Management Plan			
	(M13)	Delivery of blended information for the Demonstrators in WP6	9-DMI	Blended data uploaded and documented in I4C EUDAT			
					M37		November
					M38		December (2nd Periodic Report Due)
					M39		January
28	D4.3	Report on the TOE of the hazard indicators	10 - ICTP	R — Document, report	M40		February
29	D8.4	Second report on quality assurance KPIs	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report			
					M41		March
30	D4.2	Report on assessment of hazards over Europe	8 - NERSC	R — Document, report	M42	2026	April (internal reporting #3)
31	D5.3	Assessment report on all I4C blending strategies	5 - BSC CNS	R — Document, report			
32	D6.3	Report on climate services implementation and adaption support guidance pack for each demonstrator	3 - Hereon	DEM — Demonstrator, pilot, prototype			

	(M14)	Identify criteria for pursuing the review of the literature on the KN	1-NORCE	Internal review	M43		May
33	D4.4	Web-based tool to deliver region specific hazard information	19 - UNEW	DEC -Websites, patent filings, vids	M44		June
	(M15)	EOSC open science tools launched and final version of the open tools posted to GitHub	12-ARCTIK	Press release and portal open and accessible, software available in Git repository			
34	D8.8	Final report of clustering activities	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report	M45		July
35	D1.4	Report on the potential to scaling out the I4C demonstrator findings within knowledge networks	3 - Hereon	R — Document, report	M46		August
36	D6.4	Co-evaluation of the Demonstrators and the co-production process	5 - BSC CNS	R — Document, report			
37	D6.5	Adapting to urban climate futures, I4C Roadmap	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report			
38	D7.3	Final report on communication and dissemination activities	12 - ARCTIK	DEC —Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	M47		September
39	D7.6	Final report on exploitation activities	6 - CSIC	R — Document, report			
40	D2.3	Synthesis report on the new set of improved climate predictions	2 - UiB	R — Document, report	M48		October (end Yr 4) end 3rd reporting period
41	D3.3	Report on the CPRCM emulator development over Europe and the Demonstrators	4 - CNRS	R — Document, report			
42	D7.9	Final exploitation plan	1 - NORCE	R — Document, report			
	(M16)	S2D Model output released	2-UiB	Model output DOI			
	(M17)	Large ensemble Emulator data released	6-CSIC	Data DOI			
					M49		November
					M50		December (3rd/Final Periodic Report Due)

11.2 Key Performance Indicators

To manage risks and ensure that I4C achieves its objectives and realizes its impacts we define six KPIs which will help guide the project management team (the SSC) in its assessment of the project's progress (whether a KPI is quantitative or qualitative is noted in parentheses). They will be assessed throughout the project (during e.g., annual project meetings) and refined and updated as needed. Two separate reports on the KPIs are planned (M25 and M40) and they will be included in the project periodic reporting to the EC.

K1.	Measure the physical readiness of the approaches and newly developed outputs in WPs 2-5 through thorough quality assessment using relevant metrics for each area (e.g., skill scores, comparisons to high density observations, process evaluation, representation of extremes, impacts and uncertainty and satisfying assumptions underpinning generations of seamless information) (Quantitative)
K2.	Measure the fitness-for-purpose of I4C results from fundamental science (WPs 2-5) through to implementation and action (WP1,6); this overlaps with K1 and includes both surveys of stakeholders and scientists on whether I4C is producing actionable information as well as quantitative assessments (Quantitative and qualitative)
K3.	Evaluate the co-production, co-development and co-evaluation processes in the project, specifically in the Demonstrators and in the Klimathons, conducted through an internal survey of I4C scientists as well as a survey of local stakeholders from the Demonstrators (surveys of co-production with stakeholders are already scheduled as part of the WP6 work plan) (Qualitative).
K4.	Measure early career development by elevating at least two I4C postdocs to lead WP tasks and encourage ecs lead participation in Klimathons, conference sessions, DEC (Qualitative)
K5.	Measure engagement and efficacy of DEC activities i) ensure full engagement of the demonstrator and knowledge network participants (i.e., stakeholders) via interviews, ii) target groups for DEC have been reached and iii) ensure at least $\frac{2}{3}$ of I4C scientists are contributing to DEC activities (Quantitative and qualitative)
K6.	Measure internal processes and functioning of project management structures through interviews with selected scientists in the WPs where follow-up actions are published and internal processes are reassessed at the next project assessment stage (Qualitative)